

Pseudoscience and False Cures: When Educational Inclusion Becomes a Danger

Today, I was invited to a group of families with autistic children and children with Down syndrome that, in theory, aimed to promote the educational inclusion of children with disabilities. It was a topic that deeply interested me, so I enthusiastically accepted the invitation. However, what seemed to be a space advocating for rights and accessibility soon took a troubling turn: they began discussing the “cure” for autism and sharing anti-vaccine conspiracy theories.

According to their beliefs, autism is not a neurodivergent condition but a disease caused by parasites transmitted through vaccines. They claim these parasites poison the body and “devour” neurotransmitter proteins, affecting neurological development. To combat this, they assert that they have treated over 200 autistic

children in Uruguay with supposed protocols based on substances like chlorine dioxide (CDS/MMS), claiming they have “cured” them.

The Danger of Misinformation

Chlorine dioxide has been widely denounced by the scientific community as a dangerous substance for human consumption. Despite its promoters presenting it as a miracle treatment, it is actually a strong oxidizing agent used as a disinfectant in industries, not in medicine. Numerous health agencies, such as the WHO and FDA, have warned about its adverse effects, which include kidney damage, severe digestive issues, and blood abnormalities.

The arguments they use to justify its use have no scientific basis. Articles like the one shared in this group attempt to give false credibility to CDS, mixing correct chemical information with erroneous explanations about how it works in the body. There is no evidence that autism is caused by parasites or that it can be “cured” with a disinfectant.

Beyond Chlorine Dioxide: Rejection of Vaccines and Anesthesia

The problem doesn't end there. In their rhetoric, these individuals also reject vaccines, claiming that children are being poisoned from an early age through them. Not only do they believe that autism is caused by vaccines, but they also oppose schools requiring vaccination authorization, arguing that it is an unnecessary and dangerous imposition.

They even questioned the use of anesthesia in dental treatments, suggesting that injections might contain harmful or unnecessary substances. While any medical procedure should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, anesthesia is a key tool to ensure that certain treatments are not traumatic or painful, especially for children with sensory hypersensitivity. Refusing to allow its use without medical justification puts children's health and well-being at risk.

Why Do Some Believe CDS "Cures" Autism?

What actually happens with these treatments is that they may cause behavioral changes due to side effects like reduced anxiety or sedation. A calmer child does not mean a “cured” child, only a child whose body is reacting to a potentially harmful substance. The idea of “curing” autism is itself a flawed premise, as autism is not a disease but a different way of processing the world.

The most dangerous aspect of these beliefs is that they divert attention from what truly matters: the right of autistic individuals to receive support, accommodations, and respect in society. Instead of promoting acceptance and inclusion, these discourses reinforce the idea that autism is something that must be eliminated at any cost, even through treatments that may endanger lives.

Inclusion Is Not About “Curing”

The fact that this group started by discussing educational inclusion and ended up promoting pseudotherapies shows how much work remains to be done in terms of awareness. True inclusion is not about trying to change or eliminate neurodivergence but about

creating spaces where autistic individuals can thrive with support and without being subjected to invasive or harmful treatments.

Leaving this group was an obvious decision. I cannot be part of a space that, instead of fighting for the accessibility and rights of neurodivergent individuals, reinforces dangerous myths and jeopardizes their well-being. Real inclusion doesn't need false cures; it needs acceptance, resources, and a shift in societal mindset.

Edward Diego Vega Vázquez

Public Attorney | University of the Republic (UdelaR)

Founder, NeuroUniverso UY Collective | Board Member, Federation of Disability Organizations (Uruguay)

Expertise: Human Rights, Inclusion Policies, and Neurodiversity

Related Publications: [Medium](#) | [LinkedIn](#) | [Academia.edu](#)

Professional Contact: edvegavazquez@gmail.com